

SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL EDUCATION IS ONE OF THE PRIORITY TASKS IN THE LIFE OF SOCIETY AND YOUTH

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Annotation: This article discusses issues of spiritual and educational education in the social relations of young people who are the owners of our future in our society.

Key words: Spiritual and educational education, society, social stability, science, youth, family, national traditions, traditional knowledge.

Proper implementation of spiritual and educational work in educational institutions is one of the main factors in strengthening the reforms in the field of education and culture. Society cannot develop without spirituality and enlightenment.

The collection of scientific knowledge, philosophical, moral, legal, aesthetic, artistic ideas and ideals that serve to satisfy the spiritual needs of humanity, the nation, the spiritual heritage of the people, songs, proverbs, wise sayings, thermals, lapars, matals, sharia are the spiritual values of the nation. The system of spiritual and educational work of higher educational institutions forms the moral and spiritual essence of students' personality based on spiritual values. A mentally, morally, and spiritually perfect person deeply understands his duties and responsibilities to his country and people, cares for his people, and the future of their material and spiritual culture.¹

It is known that our ancestors have been paying serious attention to the issues of human education since time immemorial, and this tradition has been passed down from generation to generation, improved and enriched thanks to new methods. After all, human spirituality depends on education. Spirituality without education accumulates like a building without a foundation, and there is no need to comment on this situation. Therefore, there is a strong need for the educational process in all countries.

Education of a spiritually mature and perfect person is one of the most important and urgent issues of today. In this place, Abdulla Awlani's "Education is for us either life or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster."², - I consider his opinion a lot. As much as these words of the great enlightener were important and relevant for our nation at the beginning of our century, they are just as important and relevant for us now, if not more so," he said.

Spirituality is the essence of a person's humanity, a set of positive qualities in a person, the external and internal image of a person. It is a system of mental, spiritual, moral and physical views, skills and habits that determine the essence of human life. Spirituality is the level of national and universal perfection of every person, a leading and exhorting opportunity. It is an

¹ Makhmudov T. "Independence and spirituality". Tashkent. "Spirituality", 2000 years.

² Turayev Sh.N. Spiritual Threats: A Philosophical Analysis (Pamphlet). - Tashkent: Editor, 2010 y.

incomparable vital factor that enriches, perfects and beautifies the human personality. Spirituality is the feeling of being inclined to goodness and goodness, refraining from evil and evil, striving for refinement and truth, honesty and truthfulness, and following the moral, legal, educational and cultural criteria of the society to which one belongs. It is a set of positive, beautiful qualities that determine the nature of a person's life and activity and are embodied in his activity. Spirituality reflects a person's heart, consciousness, intelligence, nature, knowledge, and culture.

Enlightenment is a factor that guarantees that a person will enjoy the wealth of knowledge, education, and culture in order to activate the possibilities of self-realization and self-improvement. Enlightenment is essentially intelligence, a beacon of thought, a coach of the client, a life tool that determines the lightness in the heart, human glory, faith, character, the architect of words, the lifeblood of the body. It is the content, methods and tools for the development of knowledge, familiarity, science and culture.

In our country, the issue of spiritual and educational education, the spiritual growth of our society, especially our youth, is one of the priority tasks of our state. Indeed, the issue of youth is the most important issue. As our first president Islam Karimov noted in his book "High Spirituality - Invincible Power", globalization is manifested in two ways: firstly, it creates wide opportunities for the peoples of the world to come closer together; secondly, it takes the form of denial of national traditions and values. In such conditions, it is important that the young generation, who are the owners of tomorrow, grow up with a high level of immunity. Because ideological immunity creates in a person the ability to quickly distinguish between white and black and choose the most correct way. The role of the historical factor in the formation of the expected level of ideological immunity in the minds and hearts of young people is also incomparable. As our experts rightly point out, history equips a person with the experience of the past, the value of today and the perspective of tomorrow.

In this sense, the historical factor provides the following opportunities for the formation of ideological immunity in young people:

1. **Giving ideological knowledge.** In the historical works written about the events of the past, giving ideological knowledge to young people is reflected as a priority. For example, Nizamulmulk's (11th century) work "Politics" puts forward the idea of educating young people to be useful for the state, society and people. For this, it is necessary to give young people the following ideological knowledge:

- ✓ *active participation in state affairs;*
- ✓ *protecting the homeland from the enemy;*
- ✓ *to be at the service of the people;*
- ✓ *relying on the power of knowledge in operation;*
- ✓ *Learn from the good and beware of the bad.*³

These recommendations of Nizamulmulk are relevant even after a thousand years. In the process of ideological education of young people, it is appropriate to take into account these recommendations. With this, characteristics such as selflessness are strengthened in the minds of young people and they become socially active.

2. **Formation of learning skills.** An important place in ideological immunity is to learn from good deeds and people. There are many exemplary events in our glorious history. For

³ Otamurodov S. "Fundamentals of spirituality" T. "Spirituality", 2002 years.

example, in the book "*Military Rules*" by the Greek historian *Polyenus*, a number of examples are given.

3. **To be a person of his time.** In ideological immunity, the issue of being a person of one's time and turning one's era into a cultural era is also one of the important features. In this regard, the "Tuzuklari Temur" describes very instructive events, and by means of them, it is pointed out what a person should do to become a person of his time. ***These include the following:***

- ❖ *protecting the country from ill-intentioned people;*
- ❖ *to live always awake and alert;*
- ❖ *realizing that it is a duty to be a medicine for the people's pain;*
- ❖ *participation in improvement and prosperity of the country;*
- ❖ *providing material and moral support to the needy.*⁴

These recommendations of the owner serve as one of the main principles for young people to grow up as people of their time. In this way, ideological immunity is formed in young people on the basis of specific ideas, orientations and characteristics. It is known that the historical factor is one of the important bases in the formation of ideological immunity among young people.

Based on the approach, there are several ways and means of forming ideological immunity in young people. One of them is the education system. It is appropriate to pay attention to certain theoretical foundations in the use of the historical factor for the formation of ideological immunity in young people during the educational process in higher educational institutions.

The path of spirituality is a step-by-step path. Starting from the recognition of the human mind, he strives for perfection in thinking, ethics and knowledge. The spirituality of society, its development is also the result of a long historical development. As the society gradually developed, human spirituality also became structurally perfected. The oldest foundations of spirituality are moral, religious and artistic views. Political, philosophical and scientific forms of spirituality appeared with the emergence of the state. Thus, the structural system of spirituality is made up of the following:

- *moral views and moral education;*
- *religious views and religious education;*
- *artistic views and artistic education;*
- *philosophical views and philosophical education;*
- *political views and political education;*
- *legal views and legal education;*
- *scientific views and science.*⁵

jami tabiiy va gumanitar fanlar ham shu guruhga kiradi.

As a conclusion, we can say that the fate of the economic reforms being carried out in our republic ultimately shows how important it is to be able to organize spiritual and educational

⁴ Yusupov.E. "Spiritual development of society". T. 2001 years.

⁵ Imomnazarov M. Eshmuhammedov M. "Foundations of our national spirituality" Tashkent. "The new generation", 2001 y.

work at a high level. Because the main task of spiritual and educational work is to educate a perfect person who embodies high moral qualities. Today, only educated, well-qualified, highly intelligent and forward-thinking entrepreneurs can accelerate the development of our society towards world civilization and ensure that Uzbekistan occupies a worthy place among the developed countries of the world.

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